

Characterization of Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastic Composites Fabricated by Composites-Based Additive Manufacturing CBAM Technology

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00 Outline

- 1. Introduction and Motivation**
- 2. Manufacturing**
- 3. Mechanical Testing**
- 4. UAM Application**
- 5. Conclusion**
- 6. Future Work & Acknowledgements**

01 Introduction and Motivation

- Additive manufacturing of composites
 - Less wasted material
 - Recyclable materials
 - Faster manufacturing process
 - More consistent results
 - High-volume manufacture
 - Complex geometries

QIDI i-fast dual extruder 3D printer

Impossible Objects CBAM2 printer

01

Introduction and Motivation

Extrusion-Based Additive Manufacturing Methods

- Fused Deposition Molding (FDM)
- Large-Scale Additive Manufacturing (LSAM)
- Big Area Additive Manufacturing (BAAM)

Limitations and Drawbacks

- Slow
- Limited material selection
- Restricted Volume Fraction
- Short Fiber reinforcement only
- Weak interlayer bonding properties

Composites-Based Manufacturing (CBAM)

- New composites technology
- Requires investigation and comparison with existing methods (FDM)

BAAM

<https://doi.org/10.2172/1434289>

LSAM 1540

https://www.thermwood.com/images/2017_site/machines/lmam

PEEK-300 FDM

<https://www.creatbot.com>

01

Introduction and Motivation

Manufacturing Procedure of CBAM

All units are in mm

ASTM D3039

Tensile test coupon

ASTM D7264

Flexural test coupon

ASTM D695 Ø12.7

Compression test coupon

Tension

Flexural

Compression

Manufacturing

CBAM

0°
(on-edge)

0°

0° (flat)

90°

Tension

Flexural

Compression

FDM

0°
(on-edge)

0°

0°
(45° flat)

90°

Tension

Flexural

Compression

Support material (red)

QIDI i-fast dual extruder 3D printer

CBAM achieves higher part density using z-axis stacking at no additional time cost

CBAM 2 printer

X-ray Micro-Computed Tomography (μ -CT) Pore Size Distribution

Manufacturing

Void Comparison

CBAM

FDM

CBAM has larger density of medium-sized voids but has fibers pass through them

FDM has smaller internal voids, but also has large-volume inter-filament voids that can become fracture planes

03

Mechanical Testing

Tensile Coupon Test Results

Before test
(Ultrasonic C-scan)

After test

Before test
(Ultrasonic C-scan)

After test

CBAM

FDM

04

Mechanical Testing

Compression Coupon Test Results

Shear (45°) failure

04

Mechanical Testing

Flexural Test Results

05

UAM Application

- Investigation to determine UAM suitability
- Printed propeller to compare with purchased
- 10 GF / PA-12 CBAM printed propellers
- Average dimensional deviations within 1mm
- ~3 hours print time compared to 35 hours FDM

Geometry	Unit	2-blade		
		CAD	Actual	Offset (%)
Propeller volume	cm ³	16.76	16.67	0.5
Propeller diameter (D _P)	mm	254	254.1	0.04
Hub diameter (D _H)	mm	21.84	21.7	0.6
Hub thickness (T _H)	mm	12.2	11.8	3.3
Shaft diameter (D _S)	mm	7.37	6.9	6.4
Wing length (L _w)	mm	115.1	115.5	0.3

- **Manufacture of CBAM to compare with FDM**
 - CBAM prints faster than FDM
 - CBAM allows for higher part density per build
 - CBAM process is more compatible with in-line assembly processes
- **Internal structure characterizations**
 - FDM contains a high amount of large inter-filament voids
 - CBAM contains a larger number of small voids
- **Testing results**
 - CBAM performs better than FDM in tensile stress due to higher fiber volume fraction and longer fibers
 - FDM performs better in compression due to the more randomly-aligned fibers
 - CBAM shows a strong dependence on printing direction, especially for compression
- **Shows promise in aerospace and automotive applications**
 - CBAM shows promise in applications requiring high performance parts
 - CBAM bridges the gap between low-volume FDM custom parts and High-volume traditional processes

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